

Revolutionizing Data Privacy: The ENCRYPT Project's Innovations and Applications

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Abstract.

The ENCRYPT project, an innovative collaborative project under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, will integrate privacy-preserving technologies across three key sectors, aiming to revolutionize the way sensitive data is processed and protected. This white paper outlines the project's core methodologies and applications, including the use of Fully Homomorphic Encryption, Trusted Execution Environments, Differential Privacy and advanced Hybrid Protection Services. Through its platform, ENCRYPT seeks to address the challenge of ensuring data privacy and utility, across federated data spaces within the EU. This is essential towards ENCRYPT's compliance with GDPR standards while enabling secure and efficient data processing activities.

ENCRYPT use cases stem from the domains of Fintech, Health and Cybersecurity and through this, the versatility and impact of its results and activities will be presented. Each use case leverages the project's cutting-edge privacy-preserving technologies to safeguard data while still allowing for data-analytics to occur and enabling decision-making.

From securing financial transactions, achieving patient data confidentiality and strengthening defenses against cyber threats, ENCRYPT's use cases showcase the project's innovations in privacy technology.

This paper serves as an essential guide for ENCRYPT, where stakeholders from industry, academia and the ecosystem, can gain insights into the project's objectives, methodologies and potential to shape the future of data privacy and security.

Keywords: Data Privacy, Privacy-Preserving Technologies, GDPR Compliance, Federated Data Spaces, Data Processing, Hybrid Protection Services.

1 ENCRYPT Project

Nowadays, a substantial volume of data is available, presenting opportunities to tackle emerging challenges, enhancing research and allowing for innovative digital services. One instance involves the use of more precise machine learning models through federated learning over massive datasets [1]. Handling such data though brings about risks from cyber threats and potential misuse of data. Compliance with data protection regulations and the rigorous standards set by the EU on personal data, understandably adds further complexity to the manipulation of such information.

To address these issues, advanced Privacy-Preserving Technologies (PPTs), such as Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), or Differential Privacy (DP), could offer GDPR-compliant solutions once they achieve greater scalability and reliability, making them suitable for real-world scenarios.

Despite the potential, existing PPTs, encounter limitations before becoming widely adopted security solutions. FHE for example struggles with scalability when dealing with substantial amounts of data, as it entails a high computational overhead for processing encrypted data. Another common limitation of PPTs is their lack of integration with existing networking infrastructure and security protocols in ongoing research [2]. For DP, its effectiveness varies, as it struggles with certain query types (e.g., sum). Hardware solutions such as Software Guard Extensions offer fast and trusted computation but face scalability issues. This is particularly the case for large-scale aggregated computations involving numerous user inputs due to limited paging.

The ENCRYPT project [3] aims to confront these challenges, by providing researchers and service providers dealing with personal and sensitive data, with a scalable, practical and adaptable privacy-preserving framework. This framework facilitates GDPR-compliant processing of data stored in federated cross-border data spaces, going beyond current standards. The project addresses scalability by exploring new multi-key and threshold FHE schemes, considers threats and performance by investigating combinations of various PPTs and tackles slow computation times by offering hardware acceleration through an AI-based recommendation system. The proposed solutions will undergo development and validation in diverse settings and real-world use cases, including the complex cross-border federated processing of large datasets.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background and motivation for the project. Section 3 introduces the ENCRYPT platform. In Section 4 we present the advanced PPTs being developed. Section 5 describes the privacy-supporting technologies incorporated to the ENCRYPT platform. Section 6 focuses on the use case applicability of ENCRYPT technologies. Section 7 describes lessons learned and how these are taken into consideration. We conclude in Section 8 with a discussion of future work.

2 Background and Motivation

Technological advances have increased the collection and processing of personal and sensitive data. This though comes with challenges when it comes to ensuring data

privacy and security. As our reliance on data grows on various sectors, the need for secure, reliable privacy solutions becomes ever more important. This section provides the background which motivates the ENCRYPT project and its data privacy measures.

2.1 Introduction to Data Privacy

Data privacy involves using secure methods to handle and protect personal data which ensure that data remains confidential and protected from unauthorized access.

The importance of these approaches is highlighted by the potential risks associated with data breaches, unauthorized access and misuse of personal information. These risks can lead to identity theft, financial loss and other attacks against individuals [9].

For organizations, data breaches can lead to reputational damage, legal issues and financial losses. Companies which may be affected by data breaches can suffer from diminished trust from customers and partners, which can result in a loss of business and hamper their ability to innovate and grow [10].

Loss of trust in digital systems can also slow the adoption of new technologies. When individuals and organizations doubt the security and privacy of digital solutions, they are less likely to adopt new technological advancements, slowing down progress in fields [11] such as healthcare and the financial sector. This can affect economic growth, stifle innovation and highlights the importance for privacy mechanisms [12].

Cryptographic methods provide robust security solutions which can ensure that personal data is protected from unauthorized access and provide a foundation for trust in digital technologies. By employing these methods, organizations can secure sensitive information while also complying with data protection regulations and cultivating a privacy-consciousness culture [13].

2.2 Privacy Regulations

Data privacy is governed by privacy regulations setting legal and ethical standards for secure data handling. Such regulations are designed to ensure that personal data is collected, processed and stored in a way that ensures privacy rights of individuals while also being compliant to national/international laws and regulations.

For example, the GDPR, effective since May 2018, applies EU-wide to all entities processing personal data [14]. Complementing GDPR is the ePrivacy Directive which focuses on the privacy of electronic communications. Setting the rules relating to the use of cookies, confidentiality of communications and other aspects, its goal is to protect the privacy of individuals in the digital space [15].

Ethical guidelines are also important in data privacy regulation. Within the EU, examples include the “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, which is a framework for AI systems to be developed in a lawful, ethical and robust manner. The guidelines of the framework highlight the importance of respecting privacy of individuals, transparency and accountability when developing and deploying AI technologies [16].

ENCRYPT ensures compliance by integrating principles of the GDPR and ePrivacy Directive, thus developing PPTs which are legally compliant and ethically sound.

2.3 Privacy-Preserving Technologies (PPTs)

Mathematical concepts play a crucial role in data privacy. DP for example provides privacy guarantees by adding noise to datasets, preventing the identification of individual data points [6]. With FHE, one can carry out computations on encrypted data, securing sensitive information, even while it is being processed [2,4]. TEEs provide a secure processor area, isolating data during computation from other processes [17].

PPTs though face various challenges like scalability and user-friendliness. ENCRYPT aims to provide such technologies accessible to all, regardless of technical skill. We address usability by developing user-friendly interfaces and automated tools to ensure that even users with limited technical knowledge can effectively utilize these advanced privacy-preserving methods.

2.4 Existing Solutions and Gaps

Several PPT solutions have been developed and deployed to address data privacy and security challenges. These solutions though still face various gaps and limitations that impact their effectiveness and adoption. We outline some examples in this section.

Existing Solutions

Microsoft SEAL [18] is a homomorphic encryption library designed for secure data processing in cloud environments. It allows computations on encrypted data, preserving privacy without needing decryption. SEAL is widely recognized for its robustness and integration with Microsoft's cloud services.

OpenMined [19] is a community-driven platform for privacy-preserving machine learning. It incorporates techniques such as homomorphic encryption and federated learning, allowing for secure model training on distributed data. OpenMined benefits from contributions from its community but may encounter integration difficulties.

IBM Homomorphic Encryption Toolkit [20] offers a suite of privacy-preserving tools, leveraging the company's extensive expertise in security technologies. It supports homomorphic encryption, enabling secure data processing.

Intel SGX [21] provides a hardware-based Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), offering robust security for sensitive computations, protecting data from external threats and unauthorized access. However, the reliance on specialized hardware can limit its deployment, flexibility and scalability.

Gaps and Challenges

Scalability - Many existing PPTs, face significant challenges in scaling to large datasets and complex computations. The high computational and communication costs associated with these methods often make them impractical for large-scale applications.

Performance - Ensuring high performance while maintaining strong privacy guarantees is a critical challenge. The computational overhead required by PPTs can lead to slower processing times, which can hinder their adoption in time-sensitive applications.

Integration - Integrating PPTs with existing systems and infrastructures is complex and often requires significant modifications to workflows and architectures. This integration challenge can prevent organizations from adopting these technologies.

Usability - Advanced privacy-preserving methods often require specialized knowledge to implement and use effectively. This lack of user-friendliness can limit their accessibility and adoption, particularly for limited technical expertise users.

Interoperability - Different PPTs need to work together seamlessly to provide comprehensive protection. Achieving interoperability between various tools and frameworks is essential but challenging, requiring standardized protocols and interfaces.

Continued research and innovation are crucial to overcoming these limitations and ensuring that PPTs can fulfill their potential in protecting personal data and enabling secure data-driven innovation.

3 The ENCRYPT Platform

The ENCRYPT platform aims to redefine data privacy through its innovative and comprehensive approach to securing data. Complying with GDPR, it integrates an array of advanced PPTs, and its user-centric design approach aims to empower users with scalable and efficient data processing capabilities. Designed for the project's use cases in healthcare, finance and cybersecurity, it can also facilitate other industrial sectors, allowing for secure data processing by researchers and innovation professionals without compromising privacy.

Central to the ENCRYPT platform is a user-centric, AI-powered recommendation system which recommends the best PPTs based on user data types and scenarios. By doing so, it significantly simplifies the choice of which data privacy technologies to be used - making it more accessible to users with varying levels of expertise.

The ENCRYPT platform also stands out with its Hybrid Protection Services which bring together various services, to create a multi-layered defense mechanism against potential data breaches and unauthorized access. Complementing the isolation capabilities of TEE with the encryption power of FHE, the platform also offers a comprehensive solution that protects data throughout its lifecycle - during storage, transmission and processing, ensuring that data remains confidential and tamper-proof.

The platform's capabilities are further enhanced by state-of-the-art Hardware Acceleration techniques. Because of the computational demands of PPTs, ENCRYPT integrates specialized hardware to optimize the runtime of cryptographic operations. This improves the platform's efficiency and performance and scales up its capabilities - enabling the processing of larger datasets.

The ENCRYPT platform thus innovatively processes and protects sensitive data, combining PPTs with user-friendly interfaces and AI-driven recommendations. As the platform evolves, it will enhance GDPR compliant security and privacy of data processing within the EU, aiming to inspire further innovation in the field of data privacy. In this way, ENCRYPT is leading the way in creating a more secure, privacy-conscious future for data processing.

4 Privacy Preserving Technologies

ENCRYPT tackles the growing privacy challenges in the digital age when faced with frequent and severe data breaches. One of ENCRYPT's missions is to develop a scalable, practical and adaptable privacy-preserving framework that enables GDPR-compliant processing of sensitive data which are stored in federated cross-border data spaces. ENCRYPT uses PPTs such as FHE, TEE, DP, and Hybrid Protection Services, enhanced by hardware acceleration development. Together, these technologies represent ENCRYPT's approach to securing data privacy while allowing for the use of data for computational data analytics to be carried out.

ENCRYPT aims to bring to real-world practical applications the potential of PPTs which will help in setting new standards for data security and privacy.

4.1 Fully Homomorphic Encryption

Fully homomorphic encryption (FHE) [4] is an advanced PPT achieving robust data security while maintaining functionality. This cryptographic paradigm enables the execution of complex mathematical operations on encrypted data. As data are processed in ciphertext form, confidentiality of sensitive information is retained. This superpower of FHE makes it one of the key technologies of the ENCRYPT project.

ENCRYPT's use of FHE is not just an academic exercise but an active effort to translate cutting-edge cryptographic research into practical applications - especially in private-sensitive industry sectors such as healthcare and finance.

FHE involves complex mathematical operations that can be computationally intensive. ENCRYPT aims to optimize these operations by addressing challenges related to noise management in FHE schemes.

For further details on ENCRYPT activities in this field, the reader is directed to the following related publications [22, 23].

4.2 Trusted Execution Environment

The Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) [5] is an important component in ENCRYPT's set of PPTs. TEE creates an isolated execution space within the processor, ensuring that sensitive data and operations are shielded from the rest of the system's environment and any potential malware. TEE therefore ensures the confidentiality, integrity and security of the data during its processing phase. In this way, GDPR-compliance in the processing of sensitive data is achieved, as unauthorized access and manipulation is not possible.

Within ENCRYPT, TEE is used alongside FHE, to create a multi-layered defense strategy. For instance, when analysing medical data, TEE enables secure analysis and processing of health information, ensuring that patient privacy is maintained without compromising the use of data for research and clinical purposes. Similarly, in the cyber threat intelligence domain, TEE plays a critical role in securely processing and analyzing data to identify and mitigate threats without exposing sensitive information.

Furthermore, ENCRYPT also uses unique features of TEE, including remote attestation - which allows verification of the TEE's integrity from a remote location. This feature establishes and builds trust among participants in federated dataspace by ensuring that the environment is secure, has not been tampered with and that secure and private data sharing and processing can take place.

For further details on ENCRYPT activities in this field, the reader is directed to the following related publications [24, 25].

4.3 Differential Privacy

As a mathematical framework, DP [6] offers a robust mechanism for ensuring the privacy of individual data within a dataset. This makes DP an important tool in ENCRYPT's quest for providing solutions for projects with ethical and technical complexities of handling sensitive information.

The basis of DP lies in adding a controlled amount of random noise to aggregate data queries. In this way, individual data points are masked and a certain level of anonymity is achieved. This ensures that the privacy of individuals in the dataset is protected, even from those with access to aggregate data outputs. In this way, data can be utilized for research and development while adhering to GDPR requirements.

Through ENCRYPT's AI-powered recommendation system, whenever DP is recommended for use, algorithmic adjustments will ensure that the noise added to a dataset is minimal yet sufficient to guarantee privacy – relative to the application setting. While DP provides strong privacy guarantees, the addition of noise to a dataset affects the accuracy and utility of the processed data. A significant portion of ENCRYPT's research is devoted to exploring and mitigating these trade-offs, ensuring that DP's implementation is both effective and efficient while still providing data utility.

For further details on ENCRYPT activities in this field, the reader is directed to the following related publication [26].

4.4 Hybrid Protection Services

Hybrid protection services within ENCRYPT brings together PPTs to enhance data security and privacy across federated data spaces [7]. This approach synergizes FHE and TEE, creating a layered defense mechanism which is both robust and versatile.

ENCRYPT's hybrid protection service is adaptable, tailoring privacy solutions to the specific needs and contexts of its use cases. By integrating FHE with TEE, ENCRYPT leverages the strength of FHE's encryption and processing capabilities alongside the secure, isolated processing environment provided by TEE.

This combination ensures that data remains encrypted and secure throughout its lifecycle, from storage and transmission to processing – safeguarding privacy across a wide range of potential security threats. This successful merging and use of two technologies also sets a precedent for the broader adoption of hybrid privacy-preserving solutions – incorporating different tools for the security application of various sectors.

For further details on ENCRYPT activities in this field, the reader is directed to the following related publication [27].

4.5 Hardware Acceleration

ENCRYPT incorporates hardware acceleration to enhance the computational performance of PPTs which is an important step towards their deployment in real-world applications. This makes them more accessible and applicable to a wider range of industrial sectors and academic research.

Hardware Acceleration has been specifically designed and developed to migrate the computational intensity of PPTs by offloading certain computationally intensive tasks to Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) - significantly reducing the required processing time. An additional benefit of this work is improved energy efficiency of these operations – which addresses energy requirement challenges in the adoption of PPTs.

For further details on ENCRYPT activities in this field, the reader is directed to the following related publication [28].

5 Functionalities and Modules

ENCRYPT offers a suite of functionalities and modules specifically designed to safeguard sensitive information. These components are not standalone solutions but are interwoven to be part of the ENCRYPT's platform tools and services. ENCRYPT innovations prioritize the user and this is exemplified by modules which enable access of advanced privacy technologies to users with diverse expertise and requirements.

5.1 Pre-processing Tool

ENCRYPT's pre-processing tool is specifically designed to enhance the privacy-preserving capabilities of the platform. The tool prepares data for processing within the ENCRYPT framework, ensuring that Private Identifiable Information (PIIs) are identified in a manner which achieves the highest standards of privacy and security – thereby maximizing data utility while also minimizing privacy risks.

More specifically, the pre-processing tool performs a variety of data cleansing and transformation operations which prepare data for subsequent processing with PPTs such as FHE and DP. The tool's capabilities include the handling of missing values and the elimination of duplicates. Furthermore, the tool uses advanced techniques for data reduction and feature selection, which are essential for optimizing the performance of privacy-preserving computations. By selecting the most relevant features and reducing the dimensionality of datasets, the tool ensures that computational resources are utilised efficiently, thereby facilitating the processing of large volumes of data without compromising on privacy or speed.

Another key functionality of the pre-processing tool is its ability to perform PIIs detection and extraction. Using machine learning algorithms and natural language processing techniques such as named entity recognition, the tool can identify and isolate PIIs within datasets. The extracted PIIs are used by the recommendation system to propose to the end-user the most appropriate PPT. This capability automates the protection of personal data by decreasing the potential for privacy breaches and enhances the

integrity of the data processing pipeline to allow the ENCRYPT platform to support compliance with GDPR and other privacy regulations.

5.2 Recommendation System

ENCRYPT's recommendation system is an innovative tool, designed to offer expert advice to users on the most suitable PPT for their specific data processing scenarios. It uses a sophisticated algorithm which leverages AI to analyze the characteristics of the user's data, the intended processing activities and the associated privacy requirements. Considering various factors - such as data sensitivity and compliance requirements, the system makes PPT recommendations that balance data utility with privacy and security.

The recommendation system is also designed to continuously update its knowledge base with the latest research findings, technological advancements and regulatory changes. This ensures that the recommendations consider current state of the art but are also forward-looking and able to adapt to future developments in the privacy domain.

The recommendation system is also designed in a user-centric approach, providing a justification for its recommendation, which helps build trust in the system. This makes it more usable for non-experts and facilitates its adoption across diverse sectors, including the ENCRYPT use cases of healthcare, finance and cybersecurity.

5.3 Knowledge Graphs

ENCRYPT also integrates Knowledge Graphs [8] which serve as repositories of interconnected data, but also as dynamic models that enhance the understanding, accessibility and utility of information. This allows the ENCRYPT platform to create a semantically rich, interconnected web of data that can be securely processed and analyzed. This enables a private and deeper understanding of complex data landscapes.

ENCRYPT's implementation of Knowledge Graphs is designed to map out the relationships between various data points, enabling a more detailed analysis and interpretation of information. This capability is crucial for navigating the complex requirements of GDPR-compliant data processing, as it allows for the seamless integration of data from diverse sources across federated data spaces in the European Union. This fosters a cooperative ecosystem where data can be shared and processed in a manner that is both secure and efficient.

The use of Knowledge Graphs also plays a crucial role in enhancing the platform's AI-powered recommendation system. Knowledge Graphs provide a semantic layer that facilitates the intelligent analysis of data, enabling the recommendation system to make informed suggestions that are tailored to the unique characteristics and privacy requirements of each dataset and application of users.

For further details on ENCRYPT activities in this field, the reader is directed to the following related publications [29, 30].

5.4 Risk Assessment Tool

ENCRYPT's Risk Assessment Tool is an innovation which identifies, evaluates and mitigates privacy and security risks associated with data processing activities. The tool uses a sophisticated algorithm which carries out both qualitative and quantitative analyses to offer a comprehensive overview of potential privacy and security vulnerabilities coupled with their severity. This enables stakeholders to prioritize mitigation efforts, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently to safeguard sensitive information.

One key functionality of the risk assessment tool is its ability to provide customized recommendations for risk mitigation by suggesting cybersecurity mitigations that may help in addressing identified risks which are tailored to the specific context of each use case. These mitigations complement those indicated by the recommendation system.

The risk assessment tool is specifically designed with usability in mind, featuring a user-friendly interface that allows users to easily navigate through the risk assessment process. This user-centric approach ensures that the tool is accessible to a wide range of stakeholders, from data protection officers and IT security professionals to project managers, junior researchers and policy makers. This empowers stakeholders to actively participate in the privacy and security management of data processing activities.

6 Use Cases

ENCRYPT presents three use cases which illustrate the practical application and impact of these PPTs across the sectors of Fintech, Health, and Cyber Threats. Each use case addresses the unique challenges and requirements of its respective domain, showcasing the adaptability and effectiveness of the ENCRYPT platform in safeguarding sensitive information while facilitating essential data processing activities.

ENCRYPT use cases, will now begin to take form, and further details on these will be provided in a future publication.

6.1 Fintech

The Fintech use case is a real-world example application of privacy-preserving technologies in the financial sector. It shows how the ENCRYPT platform can facilitate secure and compliant data analysis and data processing within the highly regulated, GDPR compliant and privacy-sensitive environment of financial services.

The main objective of the Fintech use case is to demonstrate the ability of the ENCRYPT platform to enable financial institutions to share and process their data in a manner that protects sensitive customer information and proprietary financial models. This is achieved through PPTs such as FHE, DP and TEE, which allow these institutions to derive valuable insights without exposing the underlying data – which includes transaction histories, customer profiles and financial records. This not only enhances operational efficiency and service delivery but also builds trust with customers, by demonstrating a commitment to protecting their personal and financial information.

Furthermore, the Fintech use case explores the deployment of the ENCRYPT platform's Recommendation System and Risk Assessment Tool within the financial sector.

This approach to risk management is invaluable in the fintech domain, where the rapid pace of innovation and the complexity of financial products necessitate a dynamic and adaptive privacy strategy.

6.2 Health

The ENCRYPT use case for Health is an important and timely application of PPTs in healthcare, a sector where the confidentiality of patient information is paramount. This use case is specifically designed to address the unique challenges of handling sensitive health data, showcasing how the ENCRYPT platform enables medical institutions to process and analyze health data securely, thereby enhancing patient care while also complying with GDPR and other privacy regulations.

An important aspect of the health use case is the effort to enhance the interoperability and accessibility of health data across different healthcare institutions and research entities. The ENCRYPT platform facilitates a secure and efficient exchange of health information, fostering collaboration and innovation in medical research and patient care. By thus allowing secure access to anonymized patient datasets, the platform supports the development of predictive models for disease progression and treatment outcomes, contributing to the advancement of personalized medicine.

The health use case also illustrates the practical application of ENCRYPT's recommendation system and risk assessment tool. These modules guide healthcare institutions in selecting the most appropriate PPTs for their specific data processing needs and provide a comprehensive evaluation of potential privacy and security risks. This approach will help streamline the adoption of privacy technologies in healthcare settings and will also ensure that risk mitigation strategies are aligned with the sector's regulatory and operational requirements.

6.3 Cyber Threats

The ENCRYPT Cyber Threats use case highlights the important role PPTs can have in strengthening cybersecurity measures against increasingly sophisticated cyber threats. The use case also demonstrates how the ENCRYPT platform employs advanced cryptographic and privacy-enabling technologies to enable secure and private sharing of Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) across organizations. Specifically, for this use case, fully homomorphic encryption and trusted execution environments will be used. These technologies enhance collective defense mechanisms while ensuring that sensitive information remains protected.

The challenge of this use case is the balance between the need for open sharing of threat intelligence and the necessity to protect the confidentiality of the shared data. Cybersecurity teams require access to timely and relevant threat data to effectively prevent, detect and respond to cyber-attacks. However, the sharing of this data often involves sensitive information that could reveal vulnerabilities, proprietary security measures, or even personal data, thereby posing privacy risks. The ENCRYPT project addresses this challenge using PPTs which ensure that data can be analyzed, correlated

and exchanged without exposing the actual content, thus maintaining the privacy of the data subjects and the security of the organizations involved.

Data pre-processing is used in the cyber threats use case. The Cybersecurity domain data holders use the tool in their premises to clear their data (e.g. remove duplicates) and identify PII's in the dataset. The cyber threats use case also explores the use of ENCRYPT's recommendation system and the risk assessment tool, which is tailored for the cybersecurity domain. The recommendation system assists organizations in selecting the most suitable PPTs based on the specific context of shared threat intelligence, considering factors such as the sensitivity of the data and the required level of data utility. In parallel, the risk assessment tool enables organizations to identify and evaluate the potential privacy and security risks associated with sharing CTI, providing actionable insights for risk mitigation.

The use case also highlights the importance of collaboration and interoperability in combating cyber-threats. By facilitating secure and privacy-preserving sharing of CTI, the ENCRYPT platform enhances the collective cybersecurity posture of participating organizations. It enables a more coordinated response to cyber threats, reducing duplication of efforts and accelerating the countering of threats and dissemination of critical threat intelligence.

7 Lessons Learned

The ENCRYPT project has just passed the second of its three-year lifespan. During this time, we have gained relative experience through various insights and lessons learned, which will help the project in its final development and application of its technologies towards achieving secure and compliant federated cross-border data spaces. In this section, we outline lessons learned from both the challenges and successes encountered during the project.

7.1 Challenges in Integrating Technologies

One of the initial challenges faced with the ENCRYPT platform, was the integration of the various PPTs. This integration required close collaboration between project partners, working closely together to ensure that our developed technologies could be integrated and function seamlessly together.

The modular design and architecture of the ENCRYPT platform was key in the integration and interoperability process, and this approach is highly recommended to be followed in any future platforms. Furthermore, template scripts and wrapper files provided by the platform developers were key in facilitating the integration process to take place in a structured and common manner.

7.2 User-Centric Design and Usability

An important lesson learned through the project, was the importance of a user-centric design approach – always having the end user perspective in mind in the design and

development process. Initial feedback indicated that users from different sectors (healthcare, finance, and cybersecurity) had varying levels of expertise with PPTs and digital platforms. The purpose of the ENCRYPT AI-powered recommendation system is to guide users in selecting the best privacy-preserving technologies based on their specific data types and use scenarios. Furthermore, the user interface is developed and is constantly being improved to be as user friendly as possible, and to best guide users on the workflow steps they need to follow for their tasks.

These two features improve the usability and accessibility of our development, making the platform more user-friendly even for those with limited technical knowledge.

The use cases of ENCRYPT in healthcare, finance and cybersecurity are providing us with insights into the adaptability and effectiveness of the platform, as we navigate to ensure the data privacy requirements of each use case. As an example, in the healthcare domain, the platform is successfully demonstrating the capability to securely share data between different parties without compromising patient privacy.

The implementation of our use cases highlights the importance of engaging with end users, to identify and cater for their application specific privacy needs and constraints.

7.3 Performance and Efficiency

The tradeoff between performance and efficiency of PPTs is a significant area where ENCRYPT focuses on. The computational complexity and requirements of technologies such as FHE and TEEs proved the necessity for the use of hardware acceleration techniques. In ENCRYPT this is achieved through the use of GPU enabled libraries or ported to GPU code, which decreases the runtime of computational operations and also enhanced the overall efficiency of the platform – both in terms of energy requirements and use of resources.

Lessons learned from this is the value of expending extra effort in porting code and using acceleration hardware to improve the performance requirements of advanced PPTs. Of course, the choice of hardware to accelerate to depends on the competences and available effort of the team.

7.4 Community Engagement and Feedback

Throughout ENCRYPT we have presented the project in various ways – attending workshops, conferences, national events and we plan on future such event and industrial exhibitions too. Engaging with the relative community of potential users and stakeholders has been both a pleasure and an invaluable experience. Feedback from people who could potentially use the ENCRYPT platform and technologies has provided us with constructive feedback that has helped in our iterative development phase.

This engagement has provided us with a more diverse perspective than what is already present in the ENCRYPT consortium. This helps the project ensure the platform is kept in line, considers and addresses the needs of real-world practical applications – outside of our use cases.

8 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper has presented ENCRYPT, a novel project with innovations in the application of privacy-preserving technologies. It also paves the way for future secure and private data processing across the European Union. Through its integration of state-of-the-art technologies such as FHE, TEEs, DP, coupled with advanced hybrid protection services and hardware acceleration techniques, ENCRYPT is tackling some of the most pressing challenges in data privacy today. The project's approach to combine technical expertise with regulatory and ethical compliance, also seeks to strike a balance between data utility and privacy.

The practical applications of ENCRYPT, illustrated through its use cases in Fintech, Health, and Cyber Threats, highlights the project's potential to catalyze change across various sectors. By providing a secure and compliant framework for data processing, ENCRYPT protects sensitive information and also provides the opportunity for new innovations and improved services. The project's emphasis on user-centric tools further enhances its accessibility and applicability, ensuring that the benefits of privacy-preserving technologies can be widely adopted and adapted to meet the needs of a diverse set of users across various sectors and technical expertise.

The insights, methodologies and lessons learned during the project are expected to influence future research, policy-making and technological development, which can bring about a more secure, privacy-conscious digital future. As we move forward, ENCRYPT results have the potential to play a critical role in shaping the landscape of data privacy and security, ensuring that the digital society of tomorrow is built on the principles of trust, confidentiality and respect for individual privacy.

The ENCRYPT project has passed the second of its three years timespan, and we are now integrating all components together for the application of our technologies to our use cases, where we will soon be able to share more information on our real-world deployments and results.

In this third and final year, the ENCRYPT project will seek to engage with other communities and projects, liaising with initiatives where we can collaborate in a complementary manner to our activities, experiences and strengths. Current ideas include exploring other privacy-preserving technologies and how these can be incorporated into the ENCRYPT platform – to further enhance the services it can provide to users. We will also seek out other industry or academic sectors where ENCRYPT technologies can be used, and actively engage with them to see how our solutions can be beneficial to their activities.

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